

IELTS TEST TAKERS' ACKNOWLEDGEMENT AS TO THEIR NATIVE AND NON-NATIVE IELTS TEACHERS

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Abstract:

The academic research aspired to investigate students' acknowledgement towards their native and non-native academic IELTS teachers in the course of preparing for academic and general IELTS test. With the respect to participants, there were total 60 students engaged in the completion of questionnaires. In terms of questionnaire design, there were six different components aimed to elicit form participants. A quantitative method was employed, and data was collected by means of questionnaires (Dweik & Barghouthi, 2014). Spss 23 was applied to analyze quantitative data relating to the research. Research result demonstrated that participants demonstrated more positive acknowledgment to native IELTS tutors in comparison with non-native IELTS tutors. Participants' university grade, proficiency in English, and years of learning English showed statistically meaningful difference between groups. Additionally, the research findings suggested that both native and non-native IELTS teachers possess merits and shortcoming in terms of teaching academic English. All the findings were reported and concluded with tabulation. Implication of the study were discussed, and future implications were provided prior to arriving at the reference.

Keywords: IELTS, students' acknowledgement, native and non-native English teacher

1. Introduction

Conventional believes in linguistic theories mainly consider native English-speaking teachers are the genuine sources of linguistic data (Chomsky, 1965). It is not, therefore, an unpredictable fact that the field of English language education have been mainly dominated by native English-speaking teachers rather than non-native English-speaking teachers. Therefore, non-native English-speaking teachers have been the direct exposure of considerable discrimination in terms of employability, administrators' preferences, colleague pressure and even students' preferences due to the widespread ideology of native-speaker supremacy. Numerous scholars have put forward various

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findings as to which instructor is superior than the others, and not surprisingly, they emphasize native English Teachers' supremacy (Arva & Medgyes, 2000; Benke & Medgyes, 2006; Medgyes, 1994).

Native-speaker superiority has also elevated many discussions as to whether what "Native speaker English teacher" is. Paikeday (1985) also postulated the definition of native speakers as "Expert Users" of a language and those of who can use the target language effectively and successfully (Paikeday, 1985). Similarly, Rampton (1990) proposed the "Expert Speaker" represented all effective and successful users of the target language, or any language included in teaching as a second or foreign language (Rampton, 1990).

Even though students' preferences differ as to whether native teachers or non-native teachers are advantageous, different studies, however, concluded that there are no significant differences as regard to students' predisposition as to the teachers in question (Javid, 2016, Chun, 2014).

On the subject of students' preferences towards native and non-native English speaking teachers, numerous studies have been carried out as to whether students have positive or negative perception towards the "nativeness" of their English teachers (Alseweed, 2012; Chun, 2014; Diaz, 2015; Dweik & Barghouthi, 2014; Kamara, 2004; Kaur & Raman, 2014). These studies in question proposed different results about students' opinions of native and non-native English teachers. To sum up, it is an undeniable fact that the clear-cut distinction is challenging to draw on the subject as to whether English teachers are superior or inferior.

Many academic researchers and academicians have been conducting investigation on the students' perception towards their native and non-native English-speaking teachers in general English teaching practice, however, the similar studies in the area of English for Academic purposes, such as IELTS or TOEFL were paid considerably less attention as to the perception of students' viewpoint to their native and Non-native English-speaking teachers. With the attention of exploring students' acknowledgement towards their native and non-native teachers, it is believed that the study is going to fill the gap in the field.

With the emerging demand in researching students' opinions towards their native and non-native teachers, their research questions were generated as follows:

1.1 Research Questions

1. What is the overall degree of students' acknowledgement towards their native and non-native academic English-speaking teachers?
2. Do the students' acknowledgement towards native and non-native academic English teachers differ in terms of gender, university type, and students' overseas experience?
3. Do the students' acknowledgement towards their native and non-native academic English teaches differ about their age, university grade, English proficiency, working status, the purpose of taking academic courses, years of

learning English and their history of working with native and non-native academic teachers?

2. Literature Review

The researchers carried out a comparative study as to students' realization of native and nonnative English-speaking teachers in Japan and Korea. The academic research in question aimed at illustrating students' perception towards native and nonnative English teachers in terms of teachers' proficiency in English and English language education, the features of culture and personal differences, styles in teaching target language, and pedagogic atmosphere teachers demonstrated in the classroom. This study partially supports the previous findings in the same field. Respectively, the research findings illustrated that students revealed situational attitudes towards NESTs and NNESTs. Furthermore, the research also suggests that pros and cons of all teachers are supposed to be demonstrated on a personalized base rather than undertaken as overgeneralized features of any group of teachers (Masataka Kasai, 2011).

In this academic paper, it aimed to investigate how students at universities perceive their native English speaker teachers in English language education. One hundred seven participants took part in the questionnaire survey, and 19 students showed consent to the interview and were interviewed. The research results showed that more interaction and encouragement were expected from students' native English teachers. And more flexible and relaxed activities with less homework were expected when engaging in English teaching and learning. As for the students' expectation, most of the students look for the standard accent from their native teachers while a fewer number of students do not consider teachers' accent as important factor in English learning process. The research also revealed that students believe that they give considerable unwillingness to engage in activities even though students give credence to the importance of interaction (Wu & Ke, 2009).

The academic research investigated Japanese high school students' attitudes towards their native English teachers. It is qualitative research that 19 students were asked to write comment and essays in order to put these data into their content analysis. The research aspired to illustrate the students' opinion of their native English Teachers in terms of linguistic factors and teaching styles. Content analysis showed that students are in high regard of native English-speaking teachers due to not only native English teachers' pronunciation, but also the conversation they have in the classroom as well. Also, native English teachers' knowledge of vocabularies such as slangs and idioms are also given important consideration. However, Non-native English teachers are considered as giving an affirmative assessment as to delivering literary skills, grammar and linguistic skills. Non-native English teachers also regarded highly because students agree Non-native teachers have a profound knowledge of teaching methodology and showing sympathy is also one of the factors to be appraised (Lipovsky & Mahboob, 2010).

A similar study carried out in Vietnam and Japan to obtain English learners' impression towards their native and non-native English teachers. This article aimed to explore the benefits and drawbacks of learning English with native or non-native English teachers. The research results illuminated that native English teachers are the role model for the students in terms of pronunciation and accurate language acquisition, as well as being exposed to cultural knowledge whereas students perceive native English teachers incompetent when delivering grammar knowledge and different cultures sometimes cause some misunderstanding in the process of learning English. The research showed that Non-native English teachers are considerably skillful and knowledge of grammar rules and assisting students by using L1 makes the interaction easier compared to native English teachers. Some students also believed that learning from both teachers is beneficial according to the English learner's competence in English and skills being taught in the classroom (Walkinshaw & Hoang, 2014).

This research illustrates 169 male university students' perception towards their native and non-native English teachers by collecting data using a mixed method approach. The academic paper showed that the more proficient students are, the more preference students show towards native English teachers. It also suggested that students' previous experience with native speaker teachers also accounts for their attitude so that students showed more explicit preferences to native speaker English teachers. The research results also support that students show a somewhat positive attitude towards non-native English-speaking teachers due to the classroom environment and being responsive to students' demands in English language teaching and learning process (Alseweed, 2012).

This study mainly focuses on the students' preferences towards NESTs and NNESTs in the process of learning English. Seventy-eight university students in Applied Foreign Language Program were included in the research. The research result revealed that majority of participants acknowledged that native English speaker teachers were their first preferences. However, it concluded that no significant distinction was found between native and non-native English-speaking teachers (Diaz, 2015).

Todd et al. researched regarding Thai students' implicit attitude native and non-native English-speaking teachers. This academic article indicated that subjects' attitudes towards both native and non-native speaker teachers were complicated because explicit attitudes shown to native speaker English-speaking teachers whereas there was no implicit or hospitable sympathy found towards participants' non-native English-speaking teachers (Pojanapunya & Todd, 2009).

Another similar research was conducted in Saudi Arabia over students in intensive English Preparatory Program. The investigation included 132 university students in the research which tried to elicit if students showed positive or negative attitudes towards native and non-native English-speaking teachers. The research results suggested that students exhibited a favorable attitude towards both native and non-native English-speaking teachers. Generally, students showed slightly affirmative attitudes towards their native English-speaking teachers. However, some respondents

also believed that non-native English teachers contribute efficiently to the strength of their previous experience in language learning. When comparing native and non-native teachers, participants hold the opinion that native English speaker teachers are more influential in terms of creating classroom atmosphere, evaluating speaking, improving listening skills, vocabulary and reading skills better (Javid, 2016).

There was another study conducted on Chinese students' view of native English teachers in EFL context. Participants listed both weakness and strengths after the open-ended questions and in-depth interviews. The strengths of native English-speaking teachers are authentic native tongue, cultural acquaintance and innovative teaching methodologies. Research results showed, however, and participants believed that supplemental characters are expected to acquire in order to become credentialed English teachers. The research findings also suggested that not all participants are content with their native English teachers because of native English teachers' presentation due to teachers' unresponsive attitude towards participants' linguistic difficulties and dissimilarity to their local culture and unfamiliarity of the education system. The overall research results suggested that native English-speaking teachers are most qualified and skillful, on the other hand, some hindrance should be acquired to deliver the English lessons successfully (Rao, 2010).

Lasagabaster & Sierra also investigated eliciting 76 university students' opinions towards their native and non-native English teachers in Spain. This study mainly focused on seeking participants' views to their teachers about teachers' language skills, grammar, lexical resources, pronunciation, strategies in learning, culture, perspective and evaluation. General results showed that most students showed priority to native English teachers while some participants prefer to have lessons with both native and non-native English-speaking teachers. It is interesting to note that participants prior experience had a moderate influence on their attitudes. Students' specialization and complex positioning as to learn English had slightly more impact on their preferences in choosing native or non-native English-speaking teachers (Lasagabaster & Sierra, 2010). Üstünoğlu also focused on carrying on academic research students' perception of how evaluating native and non-native English teachers' productiveness in teaching from the students' point of views. In this research, participants consisted of 311 university students who were asked to assess their 38 English teachers to identify their strength and incompetence in English language education. Research results indicated that meaning and significant changes were found students' preferences between native and non-native English teachers. According to the results, it can be said that non-native English-speaking teachers were more advantageous on regard to student-teacher communication and managing classes compared to native English-speaker teachers. The research also suggested that non-native English-speaking teachers are stricter whereas the native English teachers are relaxed and cheerful (Üstünoğlu, 2007).

Another similar study reported on explorative research which collected data from qualitative data and semi-structured interviews on 25 secondary school students. The study results also categorized the strong and weak points of native and non-native teachers concerning their teaching pronunciation, grammar, and assessment skills. The

results of this research in question suggested that native speakers were perceived as interactive in teaching whereas their delivering grammar and their examination abilities. And strong and weak points of native and non-native English-speaking teacher are interdependent (Sung, 2014).

The similar study was also conducted to investigate students' attitudes towards the accents of native and nonnative English-speaking teachers. The research results indicated that no correlation was found as to students' attitude towards teachers' accents; however, being native or non-native English-speaking teacher is highly correlated with students' preferences. It also suggested that students' acquaintance with specific accents is considered as one of the significant factors to determine students' perception of teachers (Kelch & Santana-Willamson, 2002).

There is also another study investigating international students' views on spoken English of teachers in Malaysia. Participants incorporated with 81 international students attending English preparatory program in Malaysian universities. The study results postulated that students perceive Malaysian English as highly comprehensible for international communication. The study also reported that not only were non-native teachers' accents or pronunciation regarded as inferior but also, they were perceived as less proficient in related skills. Finally, the study suggested that acrolectal differences in Malaysian English are welcomed by other non-native speakers in Malaysia (Teh & Pilus, 2019).

The similar study results suggested that students show the high level of tendency to learn English from native English teachers compared to non-native English teachers. It also reported that students generally believed that non-native English-speaking teachers are less authentic than native speakers and non-native English teachers' instruction is not up to standard. The study also supported that non-native English-speaking teachers have to collaborate with native English teachers in terms of work to supplement the non-native English teachers or similar function (Tosuncuoglu, 2017).

Another similar study was done as part of the project for master's program. This study investigated the international students' attitudes towards their learning atmosphere and their perceptions towards their language educators. This study put forward some research results that teachers' linguistic knowledge and skills needed to be improved due to insufficient competence in writing and speaking (Kamara, 2004)

A further study was also carried out to identify trainee teachers' belief towards the accents of native and non-native English-speaking teachers in Malaysia. The results of the study in question suggested that native English-speaking teachers' pronunciation and accents are accurate, satisfactory for the global conversation. Additionally, it is also worth mentioning that native English-speaking teachers' accents are more familiar and agreeable than those of non-native English-speaking teachers (Kaur & Raman, 2014).

To elicit students' perceptions towards strengths, weaknesses and perspective of their preference of native and non-native English teachers, Chun (2014) also performed a study in Korea among ESL students. The research results indicated that participants perceive both native and non-native teachers as having strengths and weaknesses, and

participants did not show meaning preference in terms of choosing the native and non-native teacher. However, research results showed that participants took linguistic proficiency of native English-speaking teachers into high considerations whereas Korean non-native English-speaking teachers were in participants highly regard because of their helpfulness about addressing students' demand and teachers' elevated sensitivity. Overall results of the study demonstrated that participants preferred to be under the instruction of both native and non-native teachers, which is considered beneficial for students in their language acquisition process (Chun, 2014).

The similar study was also carried out on the perception of Jordanian graduate students on their native and non-native English teachers. Research results calculated that both advantages and disadvantages could be found on both native and non-native English-speaking teachers. Participants showed much more willingness to their native English teachers than non-native English teachers since native English teachers are considered more agreeable in terms of teaching pronunciation. However, non-native English teachers are also advantageous in regard to their grammar and writing skills. Moreover, knowing participants' first language is also the main factor of their preference due to the more empathetic environment created in language classrooms (Dweik & Barghouthi, 2014). Another similar study was conducted by Cheung and Braine also suggested that participants showed more positive attitude towards their non-native English instructor (Cheung & Braine, 2007).

3. Method

The present research was carried out over academic and general IELTS test takers who have been taking IELTS courses from private tutors and private language schools in different regions of Turkey. The subjects were chosen from the IELTS Preparation WhatsApp group in which people who have been sharing IELTS tips and their experience with native and non-native English-speaking teachers. Academic or General training IELTS test takers were included in the investigation.

Quantitative research method was employed to assess student's acknowledgement towards their native and non-native academic English tutors or teachers. Speaking of the sampling, random sampling is conducted and Spss 22 was used to analyze and for finding answers to our research questions. With regard to collecting data, a Google form was generated and a google form link was created in order to reach as much as participants.

On our questionnaire, demographic information and other information such as the purpose of taking the test, participants' experience of having been working native and non-native Academic tutors, being abroad experience, university type, and their proficiency in English was included.

In the second part of our questionnaire, participants were asked 31 questions which assess students' attitudes towards their teachers in terms of teachers' competence in target language, competence in teaching skills, cultural aspects of teachers, personal features, teaching style and classroom atmosphere.

The questionnaire employed into our research was developed by Dweik and Al-Barghouthi (2014) after the careful selection of items and instruments from the previous studies. The questionnaire first addresses the native speaker academic instructors and then non-native academic instructions. Five-point Likert Scale was implemented in our research and 1 stands for “strongly disagree”, 2 stands for “disagree”, 3 stands for “Neutral”, 4 stands for “agree”, and 5 represents “strongly agree”. The questionnaire was designed in English and no financial incentive was spared to the participants. After distributing the online questionnaire, a total 60 participants replied and returned.

At the final stage of research, statistical analyses were carried out to investigate our research questions and to find answers to our research questions. Descriptive statistics were conducted for finding participants’ demographic information, and non-parametric tests were used prior to arriving at findings and conclusion. Test of reliability in Spss was conducted and our data reliability was found highly reliable (Cronbach’s Alpha=0.877) as shown in the table 1 below:

Table 1: Test of Reliability Analysis Result

		N	Percentage	Cronbach's Alpha
Case	Valid	60	100	0.877
	Excluded	0	0	
	Total	100	100	

Prior to move on the statistical analysis, data normality test was performed, and it is found that our data is normally distributed so parametric tests were conducted for statistical analysis. As can be seen from the table below:

Table 2: Test of Normality Result

Test of Normality	Mean	Sd.	df.	Sig.
Native-Academic Teachers	79.3334	10.5069	60	0.055*
Non-native Academic Teachers	72.8333	13.2960	60	0.200*
Total	152.1667	2.39328	60	0.200*

Sig. >0.05

In order to test our research questions, descriptive statistics were employed, and for finding the mean difference between gender, university type and students overseas experience, Independent Sample T-test was conducted while One-way Anova test was conducted for finding the mean difference between ages, grades, English proficiency, working status, purpose of taking IELTS test, years of learning English and working with native, non-native or both academic tutors.

4. Findings and Conclusion

As for figuring out participants’ demographic data, descriptive statistics were performed, as a result, following results were obtained. Total participants’ number was 60, and there were 34 (56.70%) males and 26 (43.3%) female participants. In terms of participants’ age, the participants’ age ranges from 18 to 24 are 21(56.7%), namely, from

25 to 29 are 12 (20%) and 30 years and old are 27(45%). There are 49(81.7%) students who are from state universities and 11(18.3%) participants are from private or foundation universities. There is no sophomore students in our research and all participants are from, respectively, first grade (1, 1.7%), third grade (4, 6.7%), fourth grade (9,15%) and most participants are 46 (76.7%) who have graduated from universities. With regard to participants' working status, 12 (20%) participants are currently studying, 37 (61.7%) participants are currently working and 11(18.3%) participants are unemployed.

When it comes to participants' proficiency in English, 1 (1.7%) participant is elementary level English speaker, 8 (13.3%) participants are pre-intermediate, 12 (20%) participants are intermediate, 21 (35%) participants are upper-intermediate, and 18 (30%) participants are advanced level English users. When the participants were asked the purpose of taking academic or general IELTS test, most candidates replied that they aspire to pursue higher education abroad (23, 38.3%), the second most preference is to take the test for pilotage exam for airline companies (20, 33.3%), 14(23.2%) participants replied as for immigration purpose, 2 (3.3%) participants consider the test in order to test their proficiency with international standard and 1 (1.7%) participant did not specify the reason of taking IELTS test.

As to participants' experience of working with native, non-native and both of the academic IELTS instructor, 10 (16.7%) participants experienced working with non-native IELTS instructors and 33 (55%) students have worked with native speaker IELTS instructors and 17 (28.3%) had worked with both native and non-native academic tutors. Regarding the participants' years of learning English, the most participants have been learning English for more than five years (42.70%), under a year (5.8.3%), 1-2 years (7, 11.7%), 3-5 years (6,10%). Concerning participants overseas experience, 45 (75%) participants have been abroad and 15 (25%) participants have never been abroad.

Research question 1: What is the overall degree of students' acknowledgement towards their native and non-native academic English-speaking teachers?

In order to answer our research question 1, descriptive statistic and mean were conducted to all the questionnaire items for both native and non-native questionnaire. First of all, students' overall degree for native IELTS tutors is presented prior to demonstrate the result for non-native IELTS teachers.

Table 3: Percentage of IELTS Test Takers' Acknowledgement towards Their Native IELTS Instructors

Item No:	I think my native academic IELTS instructor	Mean	Percentage	Degree of Agreement
1	can pronounce naturally and accurately.	4.25	80.00	High
2	can correct students' pronunciation.	4.12	80.00	High
3	speaks English fluently.	4.32	83.40	High
4	focuses primarily on speaking skills.	3.92	66.70	High
5	is better in teaching reading and vocabulary.	3.63	53.80	Medium
6	is better in teaching writing skills.	3.65	53.30	Medium
7	encourages students to speak more English in class.	4.15	71.70	High

8	speaks too fast.	3.27	36.70	Medium
9	has too many unfamiliar words in his\her speech.	3.08	30.00	Medium
10	is not familiar with the students' language problems.	2.60	18.40	Medium
11	cannot explain the concepts or words in Turkish.	2.83	31.70	Medium
12	is less sensitive to students' culture.	2.38	16.70	Medium
13	provides extensive information about the culture of English-speaking countries.	3.72	63.30	High
14	treats students equally and fairly.	3.83	63.30	High
15	hardly understands students' point of view.	2.88	31.70	Medium
16	is patient about students' errors.	3.63	53.40	Medium
17	prepares learners well for the exams.	3.80	56.70	High
18	employs modern teaching methods and techniques.	3.50	48.30	Medium
19	uses more interesting class activities.	3.38	46.70	Medium
20	assigns a lot of homework.	2.83	23.40	Medium
21	relies heavily on the course book.	2.93	23.30	Medium
22	assesses students' language knowledge properly.	3.88	68.30	High
23	is too strict in marking.	2.73	18.30	Medium

Table 4: The Strength of IELTS Students' Acknowledgement towards Their Native IELTS Instructors

Degree	Rating	Frequency	Percentage
High	Between 5 and 3.68	9	40%
Medium	Between 3.67 and 2.34	14	60%
Low	Between 2.33 to 1	0	0%
Total		23	100%

As can be seen from table 3 and table 4, it is obviously clear that most participants replied the items in the questions with high (40%) and medium (60%) whereas there is no low mean found as to their acknowledgement towards their IELTS instructors. It means that participants showed very strong preference or attitudes towards native English teachers.

It can be seen clearly from table 3 that students believe native English teachers can pronounce clearly and naturally, and native teachers can correct students' pronunciation. Not only that, but also native IELTS teachers encourage students to speak more in the classroom. Participants also perceive that native teachers can prepare students well for the exam. Finally, native teachers can assess students' language knowledge properly. Therefore, it can be concluded that participants have a very strong degree of agreement towards their native IELTS teacher.

A glance at the Table 5, it can be seen that participants demonstrated medium degree of agreement towards their non-native IELTS teachers since there is only one item receive high mean compared to other items in the questionnaire. Most of the participants acknowledged that non-native IELTS teachers can prepare students well for the exam whereas they believe that non-native English teachers cannot explain the words in English very well, and non-native English teachers are less sensitive students' culture. However, participants showed medium degree of acknowledgement to their non-native academic teachers except for some items in the questionnaire such as 11,12 for the low and 17 for the high mean. Almost 87% of participants whose mean score

ranged from 2.34 to 3.67 showed the medium level of acknowledgement to their native and non-native IELTS Teachers.

Table 5: The strength of IELTS Students' Acknowledgement towards Their Non-native IELTS Instructors

Item	Rating	Frequency	Percentage
High	Between 5 and 3.68	1	4.50%
Medium	Between 3.67 and 2.34	20	86.95%
Low	Between 2.33 to 1	2	8.69%
Total		23	100%

Table 6: Percentage of IELTS Test Takers' Acknowledgement towards Their Non-native IELTS Instructors

Item No:	I think my non-native academic IELTS instructor	Mean	Percentage	Degree of Agreement
1	can pronounce naturally and accurately.	3.42	50.00	Medium
2	can correct students' pronunciation.	3.55	61.60	Medium
3	speaks English fluently.	3.47	51.70	Medium
4	focuses primarily on speaking skills.	2.95	28.30	Medium
5	is better in teaching reading and vocabulary.	3.30	40.00	Medium
6	is better in teaching writing skills.	3.48	46.70	Medium
7	encourages students to speak more English in class.	3.15	35.00	Medium
8	speaks too fast.	2.68	18.30	Medium
9	has too many unfamiliar words in his \her speech.	2.80	26.70	Medium
10	is not familiar with the students' language problems.	2.57	26.60	Medium
11	cannot explain the concepts or words in English.	2.32	13.40	Low
12	is less sensitive to students' culture.	2.28	11.60	Low
13	provides extensive information about the culture of English-speaking countries.	3.05	35.00	Medium
14	treats students equally and fairly.	3.60	55.00	Medium
15	hardly understands students' point of view.	2.62	20.00	Medium
16	is patient about students' errors.	3.60	60.00	Medium
17	prepares learners well for the exams.	3.68	63.30	High
18	employs modern teaching methods and techniques.	3.38	45.00	Medium
19	uses more interesting class activities.	3.27	41.70	Medium
20	assigns a lot of homework.	3.48	51.70	Medium
21	relies heavily on the course book.	3.55	48.4	Medium
22	assesses students' language knowledge properly.	3.48	50.00	Medium
23	is too strict in marking.	3.20	31.60	Medium

From the tables of students' perception towards both native and non-native IELTS teachers, it can be said that participants prefer more native teachers when it comes to IELTS preparation due to the fact that they showed high (40%) and medium (60%) mean rank while their acknowledgement towards non-native teachers demonstrated almost medium degree (high, 4.5%; medium, 86.95%; and low, 8.69%). Furthermore, there is no any low mean rank found for the native IELTS teaches, however, 2 low mean rank are found from the table 6.

Research question 2: Do the students' acknowledgement towards native and non-native academic English teachers differ in terms of gender, university type, and students' overseas experience?

In order to test whether participants' acknowledgement towards their native and non-native IELTS instructors, Independent sample T-test was conducted for both native and non-native IELTS teacher questionnaire.

As for the participants perception towards their native IELTS teachers, there is no statistical meaningful difference found in terms of their gender (M=79.34, Sig>0.05), university type (M=79.34, Sig>0.05), and their overseas experience (M=79.34, Sig. >0.05). All the supporting data and significance values are presented in the table 7 below.

Table 7: Independent Sample T-test Results for Gender, University Types and Participants' Overseas Experience (Native Academic Tutors)

Native Academic Teachers	Variables	N	Mean	Sig. (2-tailed)
Gender	Male	34	32.44	0.324
	Female	26	27.96	
Total		60	79.34	
University Type	State	49	32.41	
	Private	11	22.00	
Total		60	79.34	
Overseas Experience	Yes	45	28.31	0.092
	No	15	37.07	
Total		60	79.34	

Sig. <0.05

When analyzing the table 8, it can be obviously viewed that participants' acknowledgement demonstrated no difference statistically with regard to their gender (Sig.>0.05), university type (Sig.>0.05) and overseas experience (Sig.>0.05). All the data about students' perception towards their non-native IELTS teachers can be seen on table 8.

Table 8: Independent Sample T-test Results for Gender, University Types and Participants' Overseas Experience (Non-native Academic Tutors)

Non-Native Academic Teachers	Variables	N	Mean	Sig. (2-tailed)
Gender	Male	34	73.55	0.641
	Female	26	71.88	
Total				
University Type	State	49	32.41	
	Private	11	22.00	
Total				
Overseas Experience	Yes	45	73.11	0.815
	No	15	72.00	
Total				

Sig. <0.05

As the answer for our research question 2, it can be clearly said that participants demonstrated no difference statistically even though their mean differ with a few percentages. It can be concluded that gender, university type of participants and their overseas experience have no shown any statistical difference when comparing their mean difference.

Research question 3: Do the students' acknowledgement towards their native and non-native academic English teaches differ about their age, university grade, English proficiency, working status, the purpose of taking academic courses, years of learning English and their history of working with native and non-native academic teachers?

In order to investigate the research question 3, one-way Anova was conducted due to the normal distribution of our data. First of all, participants' perception towards native IELTS instructor was tested, then with the same approach and aim, participants' views on non-native IELTS teachers were tested with the same statistical test in question.

When analyzing the data on Table 9, it can be stated that participants' acknowledgement towards their native IELTS instructors showed statistical difference in terms of their university grade ($M=79.33$, $Sig. < 0.05$) that they are in at the moment.

Table 9: One-way Anova Test Results for Age, Grade, Proficiency, Working status, Purpose of Taking IELTS Test, Years of Learning English and Working with Native Academic Instructors

Native instructors	Variables	N	Mean	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Age	18-24	21	78.71		
	25-29	12	78.41		
	30 and over	27	80.22		
	Total	60	79.33	2	0.841
Grade	First grade	1	49.00		
	Third grade	4	84.50		
	Fourth grade	9	81.22		
	University graduate	46	79.17		
	Total	60	79.33	3	0.018*
English Proficiency	Elementary	1	51.00		
	Pre-intermediate	8	79.75		
	Intermediate	12	80.00		
	Upper-intermediate	21	79.06		
	Advanced	18	80.00		
	Total	60	79.33	4	0.103
Working Status	Currently studying	12	81.58		
	Currently working	37	78.27		
	Unemployed	11	80.45		
	Total	60	79.33	2	0.598
The purpose of IELTS	Higher Education	23	78.21		
	Pilotage	20	77.85		
	Immigration	14	83.14		
	Test the proficiency	2	78.50		
	Other	1	83.00		
	Total	60	79.33	4	0.635
Years of learning English	Under a year	5	88.00		

	1-2 years	7	79.85		
	3-5 years	6	72.16		
	5+	42	79.23		
	Total	60	79.33	3	0.098
Academic Instructor	Native	10	71.70		
	Non-native	33	80.90		
	Both	17	80.76		
	Total	60	79.33	2	0.349

*Sig. <0.05

There were no second-grade university students which has the highest mean in our research, and there is a statistical meaningful difference between first (M=49), second (M=84.50) third (M=81.22) and fourth grades(M=79.17). The highest mean score belongs to third grades. From this result it can be summarized that third graders in our research showed the highest mean and they prefer native IELTS teachers for their test preparation.

However, other variables showed no difference in terms of their acknowledgement towards their native IELTS instructors, such as age (M=79.33, Sig. >0.05); proficiency in English (M=79.33, Sig. >0.05); working status (M=79.33, Sig. >0.05); and the purpose of taking IELTS (M=79.33, Sig. >0.05), years of learning English (M=79.33, Sig. >0.05); and working with native, non-native and both (M=79.33, Sig. >0.05).

A glance at the table 10. showed the data about participants' acknowledgement towards their non-native IELTS teachers. It is very interesting to note that participants' university grades (M=79.33, Sig.< 0.05), their proficiency in English (M=72.83, Sig.< 0.05), and their years of learning English (M=72.83, Sig. < 0.05) demonstrated statistically meaning difference as to their acknowledgement towards their non-native English teachers.

However, students' acknowledgement towards their non-native academic teachers showed no difference in terms of their age (M=72.84, Sig. > 0.05), working status (M=72.83, Sig. > 0.05), their purpose of taking IELTS (M=72.83, Sig. > 0.05) and their experience with working native, non-native and with both (M=72.83, Sig. > 0.05). Once conducting post hoc tests, it can be said that, firstly, students of the intermediate proficiency in English (M=81.91) mostly prefer non-native IELTS teachers whereas students with advanced proficiency (M=69.33) less prefer non-native IELTS teachers. Considering of participants' years of learning English, it can be concluded that students with 1-2 years of learning English experience (M=81.85) prefer more non-native IELTS teachers whereas participants with 3-5 years learning English experience (M=63.33) less prefer non-native IELTS teachers. In terms of participants' university grade, 4th grade students (M=82.58) prefer more non-native IELTS teachers while 3rd grade students (M=84.50) prefer more native IELTS teachers.

Table 10: One-way Anova Test Results for Age, Grade, Proficiency, Working status, Purpose of Taking IELTS Test, Years of Learning English and Working with Non-native Academic Instructors

Non-Native instructors	Variables	N	Mean	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Age	18-24	21	72.61	3	0.367
	25-29	12	77.50		
	30 and over	27	70.92		
	Total	60	72.84		
Grade	First grade	1	49.00	4	0.018*
	Third grade	4	81.22		
	Fourth grade	9	82.58		
	University graduate	46	79.17		
	Total				
English Proficiency	Elementary	1	59.00	4	0.032*
	Pre-intermediate	8	77.37		
	Intermediate	12	81.91		
	Upper-intermediate	21	69.57		
	Advanced	18	69.33		
	Total	60	72.83		
Working Status	Currently studying	12	71.92	2	0.629
	Currently working	37	72.08		
	Unemployed	11	76.36		
	Total	60	72.83		
The purpose of IELTS	Higher Education	23	72.30	4	0.549
	Pilotage	20	71.85		
	Immigration	14	74.78		
	Test the proficiency	2	65.50		
	Other	1	92.00		
	Total	60	72.83		
Years of learning English	Under a year	5	80.00	3	0.042*
	1-2 years	7	81.85		
	3-5 years	6	63.33		
	5+	42	71.83		
	Total	60	72.83		
Academic Instructor	Native	10	70.70	2	0.240
	Non-native	33	75.42		
	Both	17	69.05		
	Total	60	72.83		

*Sig. <0.05

5. Results and Discussion

This section summaries the findings and contribution made to the literature. This study aspired to investigate IELTS test takers' acknowledgment towards their native and non-native IELTS teachers. The second aim of this study to identify participants' acknowledgment towards their native and non-native IELTS teachers in terms of their gender, university type, and overseas experience. The final purpose of the study to identify the participants' acknowledgment towards their native and non-native IELTS teachers in terms of their age, university grade, their proficiency in English, their

working status, their purpose of taking IELTS test, years of learning English and their experience of working with native, non-native and with both of them.

When it comes to the conclusion of our research, participants showed a strong and positive acknowledgement towards their native IELTS teachers compared to their non-native IELTS teachers. From the research findings, it can be concluded that participants demonstrated high attitudes towards their native English teachers' pronunciation (M=4.25), the skills of correcting students' pronunciation (M=4.12), fluency in spoken English (M=4.32), focusing primarily on speaking competence (M=3.92), encouraging students (M=4.15), knowing cultural information of dissimilar culture(s) (M=3.72) and accessing students' language skills properly (M=3.88). However, as for non-native IELTS teachers, participants believe that non-native English teachers prepare students well for the exam (M=3.68), which is the highest mean compared to other items for non-native IELTS teachers.

With regard to the accent and pronunciation of native and non-native IELTS teachers, native IELTS teachers are more preferable than non-native IELTS teachers. These findings of our research are in line with the previous researches found in the literature. (Wu & Ke, 2009; Rao, 2010; Walkinshaw & Hoang, 2014; Diaz, 2015; Javid, 2016; Kaur & Raman, 2014; Lipovsky & Mahboob, 2010).

Comparing native IELTS teachers and non-native IELTS teachers, non-native English teachers have considerably low mean in the items such as explaining the concept of words in English (M=2.32) and cultural sensitivity of target language (M=2.28) whereas native teachers obtained the high mean in terms of cultural sensitivity (M=3.72). It is also worth mentioning that participants perceive that native IELTS teachers assess students' language knowledge properly (M=3.88) whereas non-native IELTS teachers received medium mean (M=3.48). In terms of encouraging students to speak in English in the language classroom, native IELTS teachers are more preferable than non-native IELTS teachers due to the high mean score of native IELTS teachers (M=4.15) and medium mean score of non-native IELTS teachers (M=3.55).

The findings as to non-native IELTS teachers in our research also are consistent with the studies in literature. For instance, our research suggested that native speaker teachers encourage students to speak more in English and their first preference is native IELTS teachers. Researches carried out prior to this research also support our finding considerably (Dweik & Barghouthi, 2014; Lasagabaster & Sierra, 2010; Sung, 2014; Alseweed, 2012; Diaz, 2015; Javid, 2016; Rao, 2010; Tosuncuoglu, 2017).

Analyzing the research data and findings of Independent Sample T-test reveal that participants acknowledgment showed no difference towards their both native and non-native IELTS teachers in terms of gender (Sig. > 0.05), university types (Sig. > 0.05), and overseas experience (Sig.>0.05). It also complies by the previous findings in the literature (Diaz, 2015; Pojanapunya & Todd, 2009; Javid, 2016; Lasagabaster & Sierra, 2010). From the findings of our research, it can be concluded that students' gender, being at a state or private university, and their overseas experience showed no difference in terms of showing preference to their native and non-native teachers.

Interpreting the results of whether participants show any statistical difference in terms of their age, grade, proficiency in English, participants' working status, the purpose of taking IELTS, years of learning English and working with native, non-native and both, our research delivers some important results. As for native IELTS teachers, participants university grade demonstrates statistically meaningful difference between groups. To illustrate, participants in the third grade ($M=84.50$, $Sig.< 0.05$) showed more positive attitudes compared it with other grades in terms of preferring native IELTS instructor whereas participants in the fourth grade ($M=82.58$, $Sig.< 0.05$) showed more predisposition than other groups with regard to their non-native IELTS teaches.

For participants' acknowledgement towards their non-native IELTS instructors, superior results can be seen in participants' proficiency in English ($Sig.< 0.05$), years of learning English ($Sig.< 0.05$). From this result, it is clear that participants with Intermediate proficiency in English ($M=81.91$, $Sig.< 0.05$) yield more positive acknowledgement towards their non-native IELTS teachers whereas advanced proficiency English users ($M=69.33$, $Sig.< 0.05$) preferred more native IELTS tutors.

In addition, our research provides additional information on the participants' preference in respect to their years of learning English. To illustrate, it can be shown that participants with one to two years learning English ($M=81.85$, $Sig.< 0.05$) demonstrated the considerable high perception towards their non-native IELTS tutors than those who have 3-5 years learning English experience ($M=63.33$, $Sig.< 0.05$). Aforementioned results of our research appear consistent with the previous studies in literature (Alseweed, 2012; Üstünoğlu, 2007; (Teh & Pilus, 2019; Dweik & Barghouthi, 2014).

The findings emerged from our research actually confirmed the previous findings in the literature. It is worth mentioning the interesting findings revealed by our statistical analysis, participants' gender, university type and overseas experience showed no statistical difference in terms of their predisposition over native and non-native IELTS tutors. In line with the previous studies, this study goes beyond some important aspects of participants such as years of learning English, proficiency in English and their university grade and so on. It is important to highlight that our research not only investigate the participants' overall degree of preference towards native and non-native IELTS tutors, but also it emphasizes the other factors and elements of participants' acknowledgement.

This result of this research demonstrated several things, firstly, IELTS test takers considerably favor native IELTS instructors in comparison with non-native IELTS tutors. Secondly, IELTS test takers' gender, university type, and overseas experience demonstrates no difference with respect to their favorability towards native and non-native teachers. However, when interpreting the data, it can be clearly said that participants' acknowledgement to their non-native IELTS tutors differ with regard to their university grade, proficiency in English and years of learning English considerably.

5.1 Limitation and Future Implication

This study aimed to investigate IELTS test takers' acknowledgement towards their IELTS instructors in terms of their gender, university types, gender, working status, overseas experience, years of learning English, the purpose of taking the test, their proficiency in English, their university grade and working experience with native, non-native and both. By means of questionnaire, all the data were produced and interpreted correctly. Some findings in our research are in line with the literature whereas some other findings demonstrated some contradiction from the previous studies. It can be said majority number of IELTS test takers prefer native English IELTS tutors while some other participants prefer non-native IELTS teachers due to their excellent grammar skills and ability to prepare students well for the exams.

Participants university grade, years of learning English experience and their proficiency level revealed statistically meaningful difference between groups.

As a matter of course, our findings in this study hardly overgeneralize the whole picture due to the small sampling and considerable average number of participants.

Another limitation of the study could be using solely quantitative method, otherwise, using qualitative and quantitative method to perform the study with larger sampling could produce more reliable and general picture of IELTS test takers acknowledgement towards their native and non-native instructors.

Conclusively, our research findings hardly ever support the "only native IELTS tutor or only non-native IELTS instructor" attitude, however, it postulates that both native and non-native IELTS tutor have their own merit and shortcomings on implementing teaching foreign or second language even academic English.

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